

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS FOR LEARNING JAPANESE***Berdikulova Nigina Mirsolievna****Department of Far Eastern Languages**Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages**Samarkand, Uzbekistan*

Annotation: *this article discusses the significance of both teaching and learning process of Japanese language as a second language. Furthermore, several proposals have been made for further improvements in this sector.*

Key words: *foreign language, digitalization, online learning.*

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INTRODUCTION

Literature reviews of this topic have shown that several scholars and researchers conducted scientific analyzes related to digitalization of learning process of Japanese language. Particularly, I Tadayoshi[1] noted in his scientific work that mobile apps are beneficial for language learners because they can help learners to save their both money and space form buying physical books like, kanji, dictionary, idioms' books and many others. Moreover, as digital apps are mobile they can be used at anytime and anywhere, as well as helping to improve Japanese pronunciation. He also stresses that as the digitalization of learning process is rather new sphere and lack of the certain standards for teaching Japanese, this process has also some drawbacks.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Another researcher – Viviana Gaballo[2] highlights that digitalization of the language learning process has brought unprecedented advantages into the whole learning system. In fact, she stresses that language textbook publishers have previously been reluctant to join the digitization of the learning experience, providing only a limited set of online tools (e.g. flashcards and tests) linked to their own textbooks, and waited until numbers would justify their complete involvement in the business. Some of them have now made up for their delay or absence, offering language teachers an integrated set of tools capable of relieving them from the most demanding and time-consuming tasks.

According to Ayaka Kawachi et al [3] coronavirus pandemic has brought new changes into the both teaching and learning process. They describe these changes as positive trend as it has provided easiness for both teachers and students.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Our research has been carried among sixty Japanese learning students as a second language. It should be stated based on the questionnaires that the issues related with the digital learning methods were almost similar. Following figure 1 illustrates major problems of learning a second language mainly, at university and institutes.

Figure1

Associated problems with digitalization of teaching Japanese as a second language [4]

It can be seen from the above given figure 1 that lack of the network of digitalization can bring most of the problems related with learning a new language. The creation of comfortable atmosphere at the institutes can solve most of the above-mentioned problems of the students. Therefore, following study has been carried out for indicating main ways of solving those problems and the results of that study has been illustrated in the figure 2.

Figure 2
Ways for solving problems [4]

Above-given figure 2 reveals that provision of decent electronic gadgets and training language teacher for mastering their IT skills and implementing new technologies in learning process can solve issues related with digitalization of teaching process.

It should be stressed that although there are certain problems related with learning Japanese as a second language, advantages of the digitalization of learning can outweigh the disadvantages. Following figure 3 shows main beneficial aspects learning Japanese with the help of digital technologies.

Advantages of using digital technologies in learning Japanese

Figure 3
Advantages of using digital technologies in learning Japanese [4]

It is clear that digital learning platforms can provide authentic and immersive experience by spending mere expenses. Therefore, a learner no matter where he/she is they can learn another new language without being in that atmosphere physically and this is the most significant feature of language learning digital platforms. The next research studies diverse and the most used online Japanese language learning platforms across the world.

Figure 4
Online language learning communities for learning Japanese [4]

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be stated based on the above discussed research and studies that it takes some time to develop fully the system of teaching process digitally. Additionally, it is clear that digital learning platforms and apps can encourage learners to learn Japanese easily and conveniently.

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